

Maternal Serum 25-Hydroxy vitamin D and Measures of Newborn Weight

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ABSTRACT

Background: Pregnant women in India have been shown to have up to 84 percent prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency which correlated significantly with birth weight of their newborn. Mothers with suboptimal vitamin D status have offsprings with reduced intrauterine and postnatal skeletal development. **Aim&Objective:** Vitamin D through its effect on immune function and surveillance plays a role beyond calcium and bone metabolism on the health status of both mother and her fetus. The observations linking low maternal Vitamin D levels to low birth weight are important as it is associated with later life chronic disease. Adequate vitamin D status appears to be relevant to health at all ages, and even in prenatal life. **Methodology:** Ethical committee approval and consent of participants obtained 80 mothers who delivered low birth weight babies were enrolled for the study.. Their vitamin D levels were estimated by HPLC method. **Results:** Out of 80 participants only 8(10%) had sufficient vit D levels whereas 34(42%) were deficient and 38(47.5%) were insufficient as per NIH guidelines. **Conclusions:** In this study it was concluded that majority of subjects were vitamin D deficient with pregnancy outcome as low birth weight newborns.

Keywords: HPLC, low birth weight, Vitamin D.

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin D deficiency (VDD) is a worldwide micronutrient deficiency, that affects a wide range of population, including expectant mothers. The increased maternal and foetal need as well as changes in the metabolism contribute to the higher rates of VDD during pregnancy. A few other contributing factors may include the education level, socioeconomic status, changing food habits and cultural practices. The increasing endocrine dysfunction in obstetrics needs attention. Obstetric endocrinology is an emerging field, as the antenatal period presents a window during which endocrine and metabolic manipulation can impact maternal and foetal health resulting in long-term outcomes in offspring. The prevalence rate of 25-Hydroxy vitamin D deficiency (VDD) in Pregnant women of India is estimated to be 84 per cent which can also influence the serum 25(OH) D status of their newborn(1). Mothers with suboptimal vitamin D status have

offspring with reduced intrauterine and postnatal skeletal development (2,3). VDD leads to compromised length from birth itself without any potential for catch-up growth as VDD continues to affect both toddlers and school children in India. Neonatal LBW (low birth weight) can cause neonatal complications like low calcium levels in the newborn, respiratory distress syndrome, necrotizing enterocolitis, chronic renal disorders, seizures, sepsis and even neonatal death. VDD is a risk factor for multiple maternal disorders such as preeclampsia, insulin resistance and gestational diabetes mellitus, and a higher risk of primary caesarean delivery. The low maternal Vitamin D levels causing low birth weight are important as it may cause chronic diseases in their later life. McGrath and others worked on the lasting effects of foetal and early infancy vitamin D deficiency to understand the effects on later adult disease processes (4). Because vitamin D status has not been a consistent concern during pregnancy, long-term data are less. The studies concentrated more on

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neonatal effects of VDD than the later-life health problems like cardiovascular disease, cancers, diabetes, infection, and allergy. Vitamin D acts via an endogenous antimicrobial peptide cathelicidin (LL-37), which gets activated in response to microbial invasion. Rook and colleagues first noted that 1,25(OH)₂D had noncalcitropic or noncalcium metabolism properties (5,6). Both 1,25(OH)₂D and 25(OH)D have the ability to induce the expression of cathelicidin in monocyte/macrophage and epidermal lineage in cells (7). It was known that cathelicidin is activated through surface Toll-like receptor (TLR) 2, monocytes and macrophages. The vitamin D receptor element is contained in the regulatory region of these cell types (8,9,10). **Materials and Methods:** In our prospective cohort study we included neonates born during study period of one year. After the Ethical committee approval and consent, 80 pregnant mothers aged 20 to 40 years who delivered babies of low birth weight were enrolled in the study. Mothers with chronic illnesses like diabetes, preeclampsia, renal disease, heart disease, and mothers on medications interfering with vitamin D metabolism like anticonvulsants were excluded. 25-Hydroxy vitamin D levels of mothers were estimated by HPLC method at the central research laboratory of the institute. Maternal vitamin D level was correlated with neonatal birth weight. Data were presented as means ± standard deviation or as median and interquartile range for the continuous variables, where appropriate, after testing the normality. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and valid percentages.

RESULTS:

Out of 80 participants only eight (10%) had sufficient 25-Hydroxy vitamin D levels (>20 ng/ml) whereas 34(42%) were deficient (0-11 ng/ml) and 38(47.5%) were insufficient (12-19 ng/ml) as per NIH guidelines. The mean vitamin D level was 12.98 ng/ml with a standard deviation of 5.06 (range 4.65 to 26.51 ng/ml). There was no significant difference between deficient and insufficient Vitamin D levels ($p = 0.9535$). There was a low positive correlation between maternal age and deficient and sufficient Vitamin D levels, but there was a low negative correlation between maternal age and insufficient Vitamin D levels. As the p-value was > 0.05 it is statistically not significant in all the vitamin D levels.

A statistical correlation was evaluated between birth weight and vitamin D levels, which revealed a low negative correlation ($r = - 0.0923$). Among 80 low birth weight babies, 33 (41.3%) babies were born with birth weight between 2.0 to 2.5 kg, whose mothers had insufficient vitamin D levels, while 32 (40.0%) babies of the same weight category had mothers with vitamin D deficiency.

DISCUSSION

In our study, we found the majority of mothers were vitamin D deficient or insufficient which may increase the risk of reduced birth weight in newborns. Low maternal vitamin D concentration may lead to suboptimal bone size and density after birth (11). Vitamin D has an anti-inflammatory effect that regulates placental inflammation by inhibiting the decidual NF- κ B (nuclear factor kappa B) pathway, which is the main transcription factor of inflammatory mediators. Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) can be caused by maternal and placental inflammation, which shows that vitamin D deficiency can increase the risk of inflammation and therefore increase IUGR risk (12,13). Vitamin D has a major role in different foetal growth-related processes including foetal lung development, as it affects the maturation of alveolar type-2 cells and the epithelial-mesenchymal interactions of maternal vitamin D is very important in the development of the foetal immune system. During infancy, vitamin D stores decline by 50% in less than a month, which causes rapid vitamin D deficiency if no supplements are provided. As per the American Academy of Paediatrics breastfed and partially breastfed infants should be supplemented with 400 IU per day of vitamin D beginning in the first few days of life, as breast milk is a poor source of vitamin D. Estimation by HPLC is not cost-effective compared to universal supplementation, which in addition is not harmful to expecting mothers.

Limitations: The sample size of the study was relatively small and hence, generalization and extrapolation of data may not be feasible. Comparison with controls was not done, which may have reduced the credibility of the outcome. Labour and delivery information including induction of labour, and mode of delivery were not noted. Other confounding factors

were not taken into consideration like IUGR, intrauterine infections or multiple pregnancy.

Key Messages: Local treatment guidelines for vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy are the need of the hour. Interventions like food fortification and

supplementation should be developed to ensure healthy pregnancy outcomes. In healthy, asymptomatic antenatal women, it is worthwhile to supplement vitamin D, daily in the second and third trimesters.

Tables & Figures

VITAMIN D STATUS	LEVELS	NO OF CASES
DEFICIENT	0-11 NG/ML	39(49%)
INSUFFICIENT	12-19 NG/ML	33(41%)
SUFFICIENT	>20 NG/ML	8(10%)
TOTAL		80

Interpretation: in the above table it shows 49% are having

There is no significant difference between deficient and Insufficient vitamin d levels as $p=0.9535$.

Deficient vitamin d, 41% insufficient and only 10% with sufficient Vitamin D.

STATUS	STATISTIC	AGE(IN YEARS)	VITAMIN D (NG/ML)
OVERALL	MEAN	23.15	12.90
	S.D	6.06	5.07
DEFICIENT	MEAN	23.71	8.77
	S.D	7.59	2.39
INSUFFICIENT	MEAN	22.53	14.85
	S.D	2.27	1.95
SUFFICIENT	MEAN	24.88	22.96
	S.D	5.96	1.95

VITAMIN D LEVELS	CORRELATION	P-VALUE
DEFICIENT(n=39)	0.122	0.4593
INSUFFICIENT(n=33)	-0.167	0.3529
SUFFICIENT (8)	0.217	0.6057

Interpretation: there is low positive correlation in deficient and sufficient vitamin d levels, but it is low negative correlation in insufficient vitamin d levels, as $p > 0.05$ it is statistically not significant in all the vitamin d levels.

REFERENCES

- Sachan A, Gupta R, Das V, Agarwal A, Awasthi PK, Bhatia V. High prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among pregnant women and their newborns in northern India. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2005; 81: 1060-4.
- Pawley N, Bishop NJ. Prenatal and infant predictors of bone health: the influence of vitamin D. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2004; 80 (Suppl) : 1748S-51S.
- Javaid MK, Crozier SR, Harvey NC, Dennison EM, Boucher BJ, Arden NK, et al. Maternal vitamin D status during pregnancy and childhood bone mass at age nine years: a longitudinal study. *Lancet* 2006; 367 : 36-43.
- McGrath J, Feton F, Eyles D. Does 'imprinting' with low prenatal vitamin D contribute to the risk of various adult disorders? *Med. Hypotheses*. 2001;56:367–371
- Rook G. Vitamin D and tuberculosis. *Tubercle*. 1986;67(2):155156. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Rook GA, Steele J, Fraher L, et al. Vitamin D 3 , gamma interferon, and control of proliferation of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* by human monocytes. *Immunology*. 1986;57(1):159–163.
- Bikle D, Adams J, Christakos S. Vitamin D: production, metabolism, mechanism of action, and clinical requirements. In: *Primer on the Metabolic Bone Diseases and Disorders of Mineral Metabolism*. In: Rosen C, editor. American Society for Bone and Mineral Research. Washington, DC, USA: 2008. pp. 141–149.
- Liu PT, Stenger S, Li H, et al. Toll-like receptor triggering of a vitamin D-mediated human antimicrobial response. *Science*. 2006;311(5768):17701773. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Liu P, Stenger S, Tang D, Modlin R. Cutting edge: vitamin D-mediated human antimicrobial activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is dependent on the induction of cathelicidin. *J. Immunol*. 2007;179:2060–2063. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Zheng Y, Niyonsaba F, Ushio H, et al. Cathelicidin LL-37 induces the generation of reactive oxygen species and release of human alpha-defensins from neutrophils. *Br. J. Dermatol*. 2007;157(6):1124–1131.
- Viljakainen HT, Korhonen T, Hytinantti T, Laitinen EK, Andersson S, Mäkitie O, Lamberg-Allardt C: Maternal vitamin D status affects bone growth in early childhood—a prospective cohort study. *Osteoporos Int*. 2011, 22:883- 91. 10.1007/s00198-010-1499-4

12. Chen YH, Fu L, Hao JH, et al.:9. Maternal vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy elevates the risks of small for gestational age and low birth weight infants in Chinese population. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2015, 100:1912-9. 10.1210/jc.2014-4407
13. Chen Y, Zhu B, Wu X, Li S, Tao F: Association between maternal vitamin D deficiency and small for gestational age: evidence from a meta-analysis

of prospective cohort studies. *BMJ Open.* 2017, 7:016404. 10.1136/bmjopen-2017-016404

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